

A Scale Analysis of the Intercultural Competence Development of Chinese Business College Students in the Greater Bay Area: based on the ICCSRS Model

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Abstract: This research, based on the ICCSRS evaluation scale model proposed by Zhong Hua *et al.*, takes business college students in the Greater Bay Area as the survey object and conducts an empirical survey on their intercultural competence dimensions and evaluation scale. This research investigates the level and current situation of college and university students' intercultural competence from four factors of the intercultural competence scale (intercultural consciousness, intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills). In addition, descriptive mean statistics, correlation coefficient analysis and reliability analysis of the scale are carried out to comprehensively understand the development status of the intercultural ability of business college and university students, to provide theoretical basis and data support for intercultural talent training program design and teaching reform of business college and university under the background of "Greater Bay Area."

Keywords: ICCSRS model; business college students; intercultural ability; the Greater Bay Area

1. Research background

On February 18, 2010, The State Council issued *the Outline of the Development Plan for the Greater Bay Area*. The key to the construction of the Greater Bay Area is to cultivate more talents for intercultural exchange who are familiar with international rules, convey China's voice to the world, and promote mutual understanding and cooperation between China and other countries. In view of this, the cultivation of intercultural ability is not only an important part of the quality construction of commercial colleges and universities, but also an important way for commercial colleges and universities to serve the development of the "Greater Bay Area." At present, with the continuous development and progress of society, the country's demand for talents has undergone some changes, and our talent training must meet the needs of national development. Colleges and universities are the main body of intercultural talent training, which must meet the needs of national development and be based on the construction of an international talent system of intercultural communication.

According to the Educational Plan for Business English Majors issued by the Ministry of Education in 2020, the aim of Business English majors is to develop application-oriented, compound business English professional talents who have basic English skills, broad international perspective, specialized international business knowledge and skills, master applied linguistics, applied economics, business management and international commercial law and other related disciplines knowledge and theory, understand the rules of the international business activities with the strong ability of intercultural communication and the humanities and can participate in international business competition and cooperation. In view of this, this research conducted an empirical investigation and ICCSRS model analysis on the development of the intercultural ability of students in business colleges and universities in the Greater Bay Area, providing theoretical reference and data support for intercultural talent training programs and teaching design in business colleges and universities.

2. The connotation, dimension and evaluation of Intercultural competence

The concept of intercultural competence was introduced in the 1970s by Hymes, Ruben, Hammer et al. and other scholars. Since the concept of intercultural competence was put forward, scholars have been trying to construct the theory of intercultural competence from anthropology, linguistics, education, sociology, communication, management and psychology, which has greatly improved our cognition of it.

2.1 In terms of the connotation of intercultural competence.

Ruben (1976) analyzed intercultural ability from the perspective of behaviorism and held that intercultural ability Competence includes attitude, role, empathy, interaction, respect, etc., and illustrated in detail the importance of effective and appropriate communication of these elements in intercultural communication. Ting-toomey (1993) proposed that intercultural competence is the ability of communicators to carry out effective negotiations with members from other cultures and obtain satisfactory results. Chen & Starosta (1996) understood intercultural competence as the ability of communicators to discuss meaning, differentiate cultural identity and communicate effectively and appropriately in a specific context. Kim (2001a) believes that intercultural competence is the inherent ability of communicators to make psychological adjustments and adapt to new environments. Arasaratnam & Doerfel (2005) proposed that intercultural competence is the ability perceived by both sides of communication to achieve desirable results. Dai & Chen (2015) defined intercultural competence as the ability to establish intercultural connections, develop harmonious and mutually beneficial relationships and grow together.

2.2 In terms of intercultural competence.

The most influential dimension of intercultural competence is represented by Byram (1997). According to the European Union model, intercultural competence is divided into four competency dimensions: knowledge, skills, attitude and consciousness. The attitude dimension includes respect, openness, curiosity, optimistic acceptance and tolerance, etc. Hammer divided the effectiveness of intercultural communication into three dimensions, namely three ways to deal with stress, communicate effectively and build relationships. The early studies of the above three scholars provided preliminary research data for the connotation and constituent elements of intercultural competence, and provided a theoretical basis for the further development of the concept of intercultural competence. Spitzberg (1997) believes that intercultural competence includes three basic elements, emotion, cognition and behavior, which influence and depend on each other. Fanti (2000) proposed a four-dimensional intercultural communicative competence model including knowledge, skills, attitudes and consciousness, emphasizing the validity of personal competence and the appropriateness of receivers' perception of personal competence. He argues that the effectiveness of behavior is related to communicative competence, while appropriateness is related to cognitive competence. Yang & Zhuang (2007) proposed a four-level model of intercultural competence centered on teaching. They believe that intercultural competence consists of global awareness, intercultural adaptation, knowledge and communicative practice. Gao (2014) proposed the intercultural competence model of "integration of knowledge and action." The knowledge system includes cultural knowledge, consciousness and speculation. Behavioral systems include attitudes, skills and strategies. At present, most intercultural research experts also generally agree that knowledge, skills, consciousness, attitude and other ability dimensions are essential in the dimension of intercultural ability.

2.3 Intercultural ability evaluation

Studies on intercultural competence evaluation in Western countries started earlier. Sinicrope (2007) comprehensively summarized the intercultural evaluation tools proposed and used in recent years, and distinguished between direct and indirect evaluation tools. In recent years, the main evaluation methods used in intercultural competence research at home and abroad can be summarized into the following three categories: indirect evaluation, direct evaluation and mixed evaluation. Brislin & Yoshida (1994) classified competencies according to the main areas of intercultural competencies and constructed various evaluation models of intercultural competencies.

However, most scales have some defects such as difficult operation and vague investigation content. In China, the research on intercultural competence started relatively late, and gradually increased in the last two decades. However, most of the research on intercultural competence evaluation consists of intercultural competence survey and capacity scale construction. Specifically, the intercultural competence survey mainly targets students (Hu 2011; Gao 2016) and teachers (Gu 2016; Han, 2014) two groups, the purpose of which is to understand the current situation of intercultural ability of teachers and students, and to provide reference for intercultural teaching and evaluation. In terms of the development of intercultural competence scale, Wu (2013), Zhong (2013), Gao (2014) and other scholars have constructed models and scales of intercultural competence with localized characteristics, enriching the research on intercultural competence in China.

3 Research design

3.1 Research samples

The sample for this Research was 540 students from the first year to the fourth year (grades 17, 18, 19, and 20) of business English majors from the business colleges and universities in the Greater Bay Area.

3.2 Survey tools

The evaluation scale of this research is designed mainly based on the multidimensional model of ICCSRS (knowledge, skills, consciousness, and attitude) proposed by Zhong et al. (2013). By referring to ICC prepared by Byram (1997) and combining scholars' research on intercultural competence and the actual situation of students in business-oriented colleges and universities, the intercultural competence assessment scale of business-oriented colleges and universities is designed. The content of the scale includes: (1) the knowledge dimension includes the cultural knowledge of the country and the cultural knowledge of other countries (such as social politics, religion, history, social etiquette, norms of behavior, living customs and values, etc.); (2) attitude dimension includes respect, tolerance, etc. (willing to try to tolerate foreigners' different values, eating habits, taboos, etc.); (3) skill dimension (when they have language communication obstacles, they use body language or nonverbal language to help them communicate; when communicating with foreigners, they try to avoid bias and prejudice to foreigners and avoid the topics of privacy; they have the sensitivity of intercultural differences and the ability to see things from different cultures and multiple perspectives; (4) Consciousness dimension includes critical cultural awareness, self-awareness, sociolinguistic awareness, etc. (awareness of the differences between one's own cultural identity and the other's cultural identity when communicating with foreigners). Based on the analysis above, we can see the common empathy, adaptation, tolerance, emotion and interpersonal relationship of business college students in intercultural communication.

3.3 Research methods

This questionnaire survey was made, distributed and collected on the platform of Wenjuanxing. A total of 540 valid questionnaires were collected, each questionnaire was completed fully. The questionnaire includes four parts (intercultural awareness, intercultural attitude or emotion, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills) and 35 items. Among them, intercultural awareness and intercultural attitude are graded and scored by the Lecter scale, from “A” to “E,” “A” representing none, “B” representing slight, “C” representing low, “D” representing average, and “E” representing high.

The questionnaire data were statistically analyzed by SPSS. First of all, descriptive mean statistics of questionnaire data are conducted to find out the development status of various dimensions of the intercultural ability of Business English students. Then, the correlation coefficient of the questionnaire scale is analyzed to find the positive correlation between each dimension. Finally, the reliability of the questionnaire scale was analyzed to test the internal consistency of the scale.

4. Data collection and analysis

4.1. Intercultural awareness

Table 1 The development of intercultural consciousness of Business English students

Item	Sample size	Min. Value	Max. Value	Mean	Standard Deviation
Intercultural Awareness	540	1	5	4.06	0.767
The awareness of cultural differences when communicating with people from different cultures	540	1	5	3.97	1.108
The cultural identity in intercultural communication	540	1	5	3.99	0.978
Each culture has its own advantages and disadvantages	540	1	5	4.38	0.995
When communicating with foreigners, you know that you are also limited by your own culture	540	1	5	4.03	1.011
You can objectively evaluate the behavior of foreigners	540	1	5	3.91	0.917

As can be seen from Table 1, the dimension of intercultural awareness is 4.06, greater than 4, indicating that intercultural awareness is at a high level. Among all the questions, the average value of “each culture has its advantages and disadvantages” reached 4.38, indicating that each culture has advantages and disadvantages, which is in line with the current people’s awareness and cognition. The second is “when communicating with foreigners, they know that they are also limited by their own culture,” with an average value of 4.03, indicating that they are also limited by their own culture in the communication process. For the other items, the average value is less than 4, indicating that the recognition degree is relatively low compared to these two items.

4.2. Intercultural attitude

Table 2 The development of intercultural attitudes of Business English students

Item	Sample size	Min. Value	Max. Value	Mean	Standard Deviation
Intercultural attitude	540	1	5	4.24	0.760
The willingness to communicate with people from different cultures	540	1	5	4.28	0.950
The willingness to learn English well	540	1	5	4.43	0.889
The willingness to understand the culture of English-speaking countries	540	1	5	4.44	0.890
The willingness not to give up and shrink back when encountering setbacks when communicating with people from different cultures	540	1	5	4.01	1.004
The willingness to tolerate cultural differences such as different values, eating habits, taboos	540	1	5	4.03	0.913

As can be seen from Table 2, the dimension of intercultural attitude is 4.24, greater than 4, indicating that intercultural attitude is at a high level and positive towards intercultural attitude. For each item of each intercultural attitude, they are

all greater than 4, indicating that the cognitive level of each item of intercultural attitude is very high. The highest item is “willing to learn from people from different cultures in intercultural communication,” with an average value of 4.44, indicating that intercultural learning and communication are the most recognized. The second is “hope to learn English well and understand the culture of English-speaking countries,” with an average of 4.43, which also reflects the content of intercultural English learning.

4.3. Intercultural knowledge

Table 3 Development of intercultural knowledge of Business English students

Items	Number of students who are correct	Rate of accuracy
Q11	281	52.04%
Q12	333	61.67%
Q13	257	47.59%
Q14	404	74.81%
Q15	388	71.85%
Q16	430	79.63%
Q17	168	31.11%
Q18	433	80.19%
Q19	195	36.11%
Q20	392	72.59%

As can be seen from Table 3, for question Q17 about calling teachers or parents by their first names and Q19 (how you will answer questions in foreign teachers' class), the lowest accuracy rates are only 31.11% and 36.11% respectively. For Q13 (where should the host say goodbye to the guest), the accuracy rate is 47.59%, less than 50%, and the accuracy rate of other questions was above 50%.

Table 4 Descriptive statistics of intercultural knowledge

Dimension	Sample size	Minimum value	Maximum Value	Mean	Standard Deviation
Intercultural Knowledge	540	0	10	6.08	1.762

According to the score statistics, it can be seen that the understanding degree of intercultural knowledge is not evenly distributed. For some samples, none of the items were answered correctly; and for some samples, all these items were answered correctly, with an average score of 6.08 and a standard deviation of 1.762, indicating that the overall data accuracy of intercultural knowledge fluctuates to some extent.

4.4. Intercultural skills

Table 5 Development status of intercultural skills of Business English students

Items	Number of students who are correct	The Rate of accuracy
Q21	421	77.96%
Q22	341	63.15%
Q23	178	32.96%
Q24	375	69.44%
Q25	177	32.78%
Q26	434	80.37%
Q27	221	40.93%
Q28	32	5.93%
Q29	180	33.33%
Q30	46	8.52%
Q31	106	19.63%
Q32	286	52.96%
Q33	451	83.52%
Q34	46	8.52%

Q35 269 49.81%

The questions under intercultural skills can be divided into three levels according to the correct answer rate. The first level is the questions with high accuracy, and the questions with high accuracy are Q21, Q22, Q24, Q26 and Q33 respectively. The accuracy rate of these questions is above 60%, above the pass line. The second level is the questions with low accuracy, which are Q23, Q25, Q27, Q29, Q32 and Q35 respectively, with accuracy between 30% and 60%. The third level is the questions with low accuracy, and the questions with low accuracy are Q28, Q30, Q31 and Q34. The accuracy rate is lower than 20%, which is a very low standard.

Table 6 Descriptive statistics of intercultural skills

Dimension	Sample Size	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Mean	Standard Deviation
Intercultural skills	540	2	12	6.60	1.714

According to the score statistics, it can be seen that the accuracy of intercultural knowledge and skills is not evenly distributed. At least 2 questions are answered correctly, and at most 12 questions are answered correctly. The average score is 6.60 points, the standard deviation is 1.714, and the full score is 15 points, indicating that the overall situation of intercultural skills is not good, and it is at the failing level. It can be known that the overall data accuracy of intercultural skills fluctuates to a certain extent.

4.5. Overall evaluation of each dimension

After standardizing the mean value of the questionnaire data and the score of the test paper, the following results are obtained:

Table 7 The mean values of each dimension inter cultures

Dimensions	Scores
Intercultural knowledge	60.76
Intercultural skills	43.99
Intercultural awareness	76.38
Intercultural attitude	80.96

According to the statistical results and on the standard of 100 points, it can be known that intercultural skills belong to the dimension of deficiency, and his score was 43.99, below 60, which is considered a failing grade. This indicates that the intercultural skills of the respondents need to be strengthened. The score of intercultural knowledge is 60.76, just above 60, high above the pass line, which needs to be further strengthened. The score of intercultural attitudes is the highest, reaching 80.96, which is a high level. The score of intercultural consciousness is the second, with 76.38, which is above the middle level. To sum up, it can be seen that the intercultural awareness and attitude of the respondents are at a high standard, but the actual intercultural knowledge and skills are lacking.

4.6. Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical method to study the closeness of the relationship between variables. It mainly reflects whether there is a correlation between two types of variables or two phenomena in the direction and size of development and change, but it cannot reflect whether there is a causal relationship between two types of phenomena. According to the statistical results, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient between intercultural consciousness and intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills is 0.674, 0.166 and 0.199 respectively, and the significance is 0.000, less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant positive correlation between intercultural consciousness and intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills. Intercultural awareness can improve intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills.

The correlation coefficients of intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills are 0.150 and 0.190 respectively, and the significance is 0.000, less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant positive correlation between intercultural attitude, intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills, and intercultural attitude can improve intercultural knowledge and skills.

The correlation coefficient between intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills is 0.172 respectively, and the significance is 0.000, less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant positive correlation between intercultural knowledge and intercultural skills, and intercultural knowledge can improve intercultural skills.

Table 8 Correlation coefficients

		Intercultural awareness	Intercultural attitude	Intercultural knowledge	Intercultural skills
Intercultural awareness	Pearson correlation	1	.674**	.166**	.199**
	significance (two-tailed test)		.000	.000	.000
	N	540	540	540	540
Intercultural attitude	Pearson correlation	.674**	1	.150**	.190**
	significance (two-tailed test)	.000		.000	.000
	N	540	540	540	540
Intercultural knowledge	Pearson correlation	.166**	.150**	1	.172**
	significance (two-tailed test)	.000	.000		.000
	N	540	540	540	540
Intercultural skills	Pearson correlation	.199**	.190**	.172**	1
	significance (two-tailed test)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	540	540	540	540

As the confidence level is 0.01, the correlation was significant.

4.7. Reliability test

In reliability test, Cronbach α coefficient is mainly used in this study, which is also known as *The Cronbach Coefficient*, the intrinsic reliability coefficient, the consistency coefficient, and the average value of the halved reliability coefficient obtained by all possible item division methods of the scale, which is the most commonly used reliability coefficient at present.

The Cronbach α coefficient is usually between 0 and 1. If the coefficient does not exceed 0.6, it is generally considered that the internal reliability is insufficient. When it reaches 0.7-0.8, the scale has considerable reliability; when it exceeds 0.8, its reliability index is excellent and can be considered to have passed the test.

Dimensions	items	Cronbach's Alpha
Intercultural awareness	5	0.821
Intercultural attitude	5	0.876

Through the reliability analysis of the sample data by SPSS23.0, it can be known that the reliability values of intercultural awareness and intercultural attitude are 0.821 and 0.876 respectively, greater than 0.8, indicating that the data are of high reliability and quality, proving the authenticity and applicability of the survey results. Part of the questionnaire has passed the reliability test.

5. Conclusion

In combination with the actual situation of students in business colleges and universities, this research adopts Zhong Hua's localization ICCSRS evaluation scale, and uses descriptive mean statistics and correlation coefficient analysis, which are widely accepted by international statisticians as statistical tools to evaluate the current situation of intercultural ability of college students in business colleges and universities. The research results show that the overall level of intercultural ability of business English majors in the Greater Bay area is not high, between low and average level. First of all, college students have strong intercultural awareness. For example, they believe that each culture has its advantages and disadvantages, are willing to communicate and learn from foreigners from different cultures, and will not give up or shrink back when they encounter setbacks in communication with people from different cultures. However, when communicating with people from different social and cultural backgrounds and fields, they are not quite clear about their own cultural identity and whether they can objectively evaluate the behavior of foreigners. Secondly, college students lack the ability to master certain local cultural knowledge and need to improve it. Therefore, this research is of great significance. It can help students to better realize the strength of their own intercultural ability, or help them to have a self-awareness of their intercultural ability (that is, many scholars pay attention to factors in the study of intercultural ability). At the same time, it provides strong data support for talent cultivation plan and curriculum setting of business colleges in the Great Bay Area, provides theoretical basis and experience reference for intercultural teaching reform, and provides meaningful empirical data for subsequent related studies.

References

- Arasaratnam, L.A. & Doerfel, M.L. (2005). International communication competence: Identifying key components from multicultural perspective. *International Journal of International Relations*, 29, 137-163.
- Black J S, Mendenhall M & Oddou G. (1991). Toward a comprehensive model of international adjustment: An integration of multiple theoretical perspectives. *Academy of Management Review*, 16, 291—317.
- Byam, M. (1997). *Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingua, 58.
- Cai, J, & Chen, N. (2013). Demand Analysis of ESP in the Context of Internationalization of Higher Education. *Audio-visual Teaching of Foreign Languages*, (9), 3-9. [蔡基刚, 陈宁阳.(2013). 高等教育国际化背景下的专门用途英语需求分析. *外语电化教学*, (9):3—9.]
- Chen, G.M.&W.J. Starosta. (2007). *Foundations of International Communication*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press. 36-59.
- Dai, X. (2018). *The Study of intercultural competence*. Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press, 36. 戴晓东. (2018). 跨文化能力研究. 外语教学与研究出版社, 36.
- Fan W. , Wu W.& Peng R. (2013). An analysis of self-evaluation of Intercultural competence among Chinese college students. *Chinese Foreign Languages*, (6) :53-59. 樊葳葳, 吴卫平, 彭仁忠. (2013). 中国大学生跨文化能力自我评价分析. *中国外语*, 10(06):53-59.
- Fantini, A. E. (2006). Exploring and Assessing Intercultural Competence [EB/OL] . Retrieved June 13, 2010, from http://www.Sit.edu/SITOccasionalPapers/feil_research_report.pdf. 2006.
- Hu W. (2013). How to Position Intercultural Communicative Competence in Foreign Language Teaching. *Foreign Language Community*, (6) :2-8. 胡文仲. (2013). [跨文化交际能力在外语教学中如何定位 [J] . *外语界*, (6):2—8.]
- Hymes, D. On communicative competence. In pride, J. B. & Holmes, J. (Ed) *Sociolinguistics*. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1972:169-93
- Peng R. & Wu W. (2017). An Analysis of the Development of College Students' intercultural competence under the Background of "One Belt and One Road" Strategy. *Hubei minority Journal of College of Philosophy and Social Sciences*, 35(3) :183-188. [彭仁忠, 吴卫平. (2017). “一带一路”战略背景下大学生跨文化能力发展分析. *湖北民族学院学报 (哲学社会科学版)*, 35(3):183-188.]
- Shi X. (2009). Study on the theory of intercultural language socialization. *Chinese Foreign Language*, 6(01) :85-89. [史兴松. (2009). 跨文化语言社会化理论初探. *中国外语*, 6(01):85—89.]
- Shi X. (2014). An Analysis of the social Needs of Foreign language Competence and Intercultural Communication Competence. *Foreign Language Community*, (06) :79-86. [史兴松. (2014). 外语能力与跨文化交际能力社会需求分析. *外语界*, (6):79—86.]
- Spizberg, B. H. & G Changnon. (2009). Conceptualizing intercultural competence. In Deardorff, D.K. (Eds) *The SAGE Handbook of Intercultural Competence*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 2-52.
- Ting-Toomey, S. (1993). Communicative resourcefulness: An identity negotiation perspective. In Wiseman, R.I. & Koester, J. (Eds) *Intercultural communication theory*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 1993:72-111.
- Wu W., Fan W. & Peng R. (2013). An Analysis of Intercultural Competence dimensions and Evaluation Scale of Chinese College Students. *Foreign Language Teaching Science and Research*, 45(04) : 581-593. [吴卫平, 樊葳葳, 彭仁忠. (2013). 中国大学生跨文化能力维度及评价量表分析. *外语教学与研究*, 45(04) : 581-593.]
- Wu W. (2013). Research on comprehensive Evaluation of Chinese College Students' Intercultural Competence . *Huazhong University of Science and Technology*, (07):194. [吴卫平. (2015). 中国大学生跨文化能力综合评价研究. *华中科技大学*, (07):194]
- Xu L. (2000). On intercultural communication competence. *Foreign Language and Foreign Language Teaching*, (07) : 17-20. [许力生. (2000). 跨文化的交际能力问题探讨. *外语与外语教学*, (07) :17-20.]

Appendix 1: Survey**Questionnaire on Cross-cultural Communication**
(Intercultural Knowledge and Competence Questionnaire)**I. Intercultural awareness**

1. The awareness of cultural differences when communicating with people from different cultures.

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

2. One's cultural identity in cross-cultural communication.

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

3. Each culture has its advantages and disadvantages.

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

4. Know that you are also limited by your own culture when communicating with foreigners.

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

5. I can objectively evaluate the behavior of foreigners.

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

II. Second, cross-cultural attitude

6. Willingness to communicate with people from different cultures

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

7. I hope to learn English well and understand the culture of English-speaking countries

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

8. Willingness to learn from people from different cultures in cross-cultural communication

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

9. Never give up or shrink back when encountering setbacks when communicating with people from different cultures

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

10. I can tolerate cultural differences such as different values, eating habits and taboos

- A. No
- B. General
- C. Higher

III. Three, cross-cultural knowledge

11. If you are invited to a 6 o'clock dinner party at an American friend's home, what time is appropriate for you to go?

- A. 5:30 p.m.
- B. 6:00 p.m.
- C. 7:00 p.m.

12. A Western friend has invited you to his home. When is the proper time for you to leave when the party is coming to an end?

- A. twenty minutes after you have informed the host and the hostess about your leaving
- B. immediately after you informed the host and the hostess
- C. anytime when you plan to leave

13. In the West, where should the guests go when they say goodbye? Do you think so?

- A. The door
- B. Outside the door
- C. Can be

14. What does an American mean when he shrugs?

- A. I'll think about it
- B. Sorry, I don't know
- C. I'm not feeling well

15. Do you think it is ok to cross your legs while sitting and talking to British people?

- A. Absolutely not
- B. can
- C. I don't know

16. What do you mean by nodding your head and shaking hands in different countries?

- A. The same
- B. Different
- C. Similar

17. In British and American countries, can students call their teachers or children call their parents by their first names?

- A. Yes.
- B. No.
- C. Yes, but it's not polite

18. What do westerners usually bring when they are ill in hospital?

- A. Flowers
- B. Nourishment or money
- C. Anything

19. When you answer a question in diplomacy class, what do you do?

- A. Sitting
- B. Stand up immediately
- C. Hesitate before you stand up

20. When an English friend gives you a present, what do you do?

- A. Say thank you and put the gift aside
- B. Say thank you and open your gift right away
- C. Don't know how to express your feelings

IV. Cross-cultural skills

21. "Thank you so much for everything you've done for me in the last few days," says a foreign client expressing gratitude to your Chinese boss. Your boss politely replies in Chinese, "It's our duty." As the boss's interpreter, how will you translate what the boss says?
- It's our duty to help you.
 - It is our pleasure
 - It is our job to do so.
22. If an American complimented you on your beautiful dress, what would you say?
- I'm glad you like it and you can take it if you want to.
 - Oh, it's cheap.
 - Thank you. I like it too.
23. You and some American colleagues are waiting for the elevator. When the elevator comes, you want them to get in first. How would you put it?
- Go ahead
 - Please
 - After you
24. If two Americans were speaking in front of you and you wanted to go around them, what would you do or say to them?
- Sorry. Would you let me pass?
 - Excuse me.
 - I am sorry.
25. In western countries, when a friend asks you, "Can you come to my birthday party? You're not sure if you can go, you say,
- I am not sure.
 - May I let you know this evening?
 - I don't know.
26. When you are invited to your best friend Amy's birthday party, but you have a lot of homework to do, what will you say?
- I'm sorry. I have to do lots of homework then.
 - Oh! I'm sorry. I'm afraid I can't come because I've something else to do and I can hardly postpone it.
 - I can't accept your invitation because I've lots of homework to do.
27. When you meet your foreign teacher Peter, how do you greet him?
- Hello, Peter
 - Hi, teacher.
 - Hi, Peter, where do you want to go?
28. What will you do if you are late for a social event?
- Apologize to those who have already been there
 - Say nothing at all
 - Be seated directly and forget it
29. What will you do when your British foreign teacher explains something in class but you don't understand it?
- Nod your head and smile.
 - look at them blankly.
 - Say "I am sorry. I don't understand. Could you please give an example?"
30. When you visit a Westerner's home and the host wants to hang up your coat, what will you do?
- No, thank you.
 - Yes, please, thank you.
 - Don't bother yourself to hang my coat, let me do it.
31. In the West, what should the guest do when the host brings him a cup of tea?
- Stand up and say "thank you"
 - Remain seated and say nothing
 - Remain seated and receive it with a smile and say thank you
32. If you're eating with a foreigner and want something from the other side of the table. What would you say?
- Stand up and stretch out your hand to it yourself.
 - Say, "Excuse me, could you pass the X, please?"
 - Say, "Sorry, could you pass the X, please?"
33. I'd like to say goodbye to you.
- You can stay a little longer
 - Say hello to your parents for me
 - You walk slowly
34. Are you sick? Are you sick? You will say:
- Are you sick?
 - You seem rather tired, are you ok?
 - You seem ill. You should see a doctor.
35. What will you do if you are late for a Western social event?
- Apologize to those who have already been here
 - Say nothing at all
 - Be seated directly and forget it